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Preprocessing of ESTEC photon counts simulations, Run No 9

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The 9th run of IDT photon counts simulations by ESTEC (letter by S Vaghi, 1985 Nov 29) has been reduced with the IDT Preprocessing software at Lund Observatory (see NDAC/LO/061 for a description). Two reductions were made: the first one using the binning algorithm with 45 bins, the second one without binning. The results of the first reduction should be virtually identical to those obtained at RGO, while the second reduction should be similar to the one at CSS. The assumed scan velocity is 168.75 as/s.

The contents and format of the output are the same as described in NDAC/LO/061, except that a new statistic, t_0 , has been added in the fifth line (before t_1). t_0 indicates the presence of any modulation in the signal. It is the chi-square calculated on the hypothesis that the signal is not modulated (a homogeneous Poisson process), but transformed to a quasi-normal variable similarly to t_1 [equation (6) in NDAC/LO/061]. Thus, if there is no modulation, t_0 is expected to be unit normal. Conversely, if $t_0 \gtrsim 3$, some kind of modulation is clearly indicated. It should be noted that this test (of any kind of modulation) is much less sensitive than a test for a particular kind of modulation, such as a sinusoidal modulation with given period. Therefore, t_0 may be less than 3 even though the sinusoidal modulation is quite significant.

The tables below give some statistics of the two reductions and of the difference between them. Some tendencies seen already in previous runs are confirmed: The binned solution degrades the result a little bit for the bright stars, but not at all for the faint stars; the Cramér-Rao limit is practically reached for the bright stars but not quite for the faint, especially in the second harmonic (Table 2b). It can also be remarked that on the basis of a $t_0 < 3$ criterion, practically all the observations of the faint stars would be considered to have no modulation. Clearly, this is not a very useful rejection criterion.

Table 1a. Extreme and rms values of the actual phase errors (Δp_1 , Δp_2) in the two reductions, and of the differences between the solutions. Bright stars only (2375 observations). Unit: mas.

	binned		not binned		binned - not binned	
	Δp_1	Δp_2	Δp_1	Δp_2	Δp_1	Δp_2
minimum	-37.8	-174.6	-32.4	-190.1	-5.6	-24.6
maximum	45.9	235.8	44.8	230.9	5.4	167.1
rms value	7.3	15.3	7.2	15.7	1.0	3.8
Correlation between binned and not binned solutions:					0.9904	0.9700

Table 1b. Same as Table 1a but for the faint stars (894 observations)

	binned		not binned		binned - not binned	
	Δp_1	Δp_2	Δp_1	Δp_2	Δp_1	Δp_2
minimum	-242.5	-483.4	-247.3	-482.5	-15.8	-128.6
maximum	291.8	414.5	298.8	416.2	13.4	140.2
rms value	60.2	108.6	60.2	109.2	2.9	12.7
Correlation between binned and not binned solutions:					0.9989	0.9781

Table 2a. Mean and rms values of t_0 , t_1 , and normalised phase errors, bright stars, binned solution

	t_0	t_1	$\Delta p_1 / \sigma_{p1}$	$\Delta p_2 / \sigma_{p2}$
mean value	26.5	0.02	-0.011	-0.005
rms value	28.6	1.00	1.013	1.016

Table 2b. Same as Table 2a but for faint stars-

	t_0	t_1	$\Delta p_1 / \sigma_{p1}$	$\Delta p_2 / \sigma_{p2}$
mean value	1.76	0.00	0.016	-0.003
rms value	2.12	0.95	1.028	1.629

file 1 = ulbin
file 2 = ulnon

Number of observations = 894
(faint stars)

STATISTICS, FILE = 1

Mean values:

84.9	598.7	1164.9	189.1	74.1	32.7	.6116	.6306	.6167
			14.79	21.36	20.35	.0533	.0591	.0879
						.0006	.0007	.0003
.00	.00	.00		1.76	.00	.0024	.0163	-.0032

RMS values:

516.9	637.4	1262.1	189.7	77.1	36.7	.7189	.7351	.7206
			15.06	21.75	20.72	.0619	.0686	.1306
						.0596	.0602	.1086
.00	.00	.00		2.12	.95	1.1566	1.0284	1.6288

Minimum values:

-860.0	1.0	640.0	143.5	7.8	2.1	.0013	.0022	.0016
			9.10	13.20	12.70	.0217	.0255	.0188
						-.3027	-.2425	-.4834
.00	.00	.00		-1.71	-3.15	-3.6200	-3.4300	-7.6500

Maximum values:

900.0	783.0	2560.0	247.5	143.4	91.2	1.2068	1.2080	1.2060
			21.50	30.70	30.20	.4310	.5746	1.1517
						.2331	.2918	.4145
.00	.00	.00		5.60	3.28	4.0600	3.7300	13.9800

STATISTICS, FILE = 2

Mean values:

84.9	598.7	1164.9	189.1	74.2	32.9	.6114	.6266	.6184
			14.79	21.35	20.35	.0535	.0590	.0887
						.0004	.0007	-.0007
.00	.00	.00		.40	.05	-.0015	.0161	-.0025

RMS values:

516.9	637.4	1262.1	189.6	77.2	36.9	.7187	.7318	.7220
			15.06	21.75	20.72	.0643	.0686	.1471
						.0597	.0602	.1092
.00	.00	.00		1.10	1.00	1.1628	1.0301	1.6357

Minimum values:

-860.0	1.0	640.0	143.7	7.7	1.1	.0003	.0001	.0016
			9.10	13.10	12.70	.0216	.0252	.0181
						-.3061	-.2473	-.4825

.00 .00 .00 -3.12 -3.39 -3.6300 -3.5300 -8.1800

Maximum values:

900.0 783.0 2560.0 247.5 144.3 94.1 1.2080 1.2075 1.2064
 21.50 30.70 30.20 .5906 .5837 2.3209
 .2377 .2988 .4162
 .00 .00 .00 4.44 3.47 3.9900 3.8600 14.4400

STATISTICS OF DIFFERENCE, FILE 1 - FILE 2

Mean values:

.0 .0 .0 .0 -.1 -.1 .0002 .0000 .0003
 .00 .00 .00 -.0002 .0001 -.0008
 .0002 .0000 .0003
 .00 .00 .00 1.36 -.05 .0039 .0002 -.0006

MS values:

.0 .0 .0 .2 .9 1.7 .0089 .0029 .0127
 .04 .10 .05 .0149 .0018 .0627
 .0089 .0029 .0127
 .00 .00 .00 1.94 1.24 .1200 .0492 .3416

Minimum values:

.0 .0 .0 -.7 -3.2 -6.5 -.1530 -.0158 -.1287
 -.10 -.40 -.10 -.3170 -.0190 -1.2712
 -.1531 -.0158 -.1286
 .00 .00 .00 -3.24 -4.60 -1.4700 -.1800 -9.2100

Maximum values:

.0 .0 .0 .8 3.5 6.0 .1364 .0134 .1403
 .10 .40 .20 .1726 .0126 .8187
 .1364 .0134 .1402
 .00 .00 .00 5.75 3.92 1.6700 .1600 1.6000

Correlation coefficients:

1.0000 1.0000 1.0000 1.0000 .9999 .9990 .9999 1.0000 .9998
 1.0000 1.0000 1.0000 .9729 .9996 .9049
 .9889 .9989 .9932
 .0000 .0000 .0000 .4156 .1852 .9947 .9989 .9781

file 1 = utbin
file 2 = utnon

Number of observations = 2375
(bright stars)

STATISTICS; FILE = 1

Mean values:

-48.8	557.7	515.4	10329.3	7470.3	2146.2	.6062	.6041	.6092
			198.27	292.40	260.78	.0071	.0068	.0133
.00	.00	.00	.00	26.53	.02	-.0002	-.0002	-.0002
						-.0119	-.0111	-.0053

RMS values:

510.2	608.2	725.3	10331.6	7482.2	2191.3	.7003	.6986	.7029
			213.32	314.26	280.49	.0102	.0074	.0307
.00	.00	.00	.00	28.62	1.00	.0076	.0073	.0153
						1.0181	1.0132	1.0163

Minimum values:

-900.0	3.0	48.0	9389.1	5889.4	46.1	.0004	.0004	.0004
			68.90	100.80	90.00	.0021	.0022	.0032
.00	.00	.00	.00	6.26	-3.31	-.0548	-.0378	-.1746
						-3.5300	-3.5200	-3.4900

Maximum values:

900.0	785.0	2560.0	11511.5	9612.5	3722.9	1.2076	1.2076	1.2065
			541.20	816.90	715.50	.3230	.0199	1.2739
.00	.00	.00	.00	61.79	3.97	.0454	.0459	.2358
						3.3400	3.4400	3.1500

STATISTICS; FILE = 2

Mean values:

-48.8	557.7	515.4	10329.6	7477.0	2153.1	.6067	.6052	.6057
			198.23	292.42	260.69	.0070	.0068	.0131
.00	.00	.00	.00	22.67	.03	-.0001	-.0001	-.0002
						-.0098	-.0085	-.0048

RMS values:

510.2	608.2	725.3	10331.8	7489.0	2197.9	.7008	.6995	.7024
			213.24	314.21	280.35	.0093	.0074	.0259
.00	.00	.00	.00	24.74	1.00	.0075	.0072	.0157
						1.0101	1.0037	1.0164

Minimum values:

-900.0	3.0	48.0	9368.9	5828.9	58.2	.0003	.0005	.0000
			68.90	100.80	90.00	.0021	.0022	.0032
						-.0533	-.0324	-.1901

.00 .00 .00 5.97 -3.51 -3.3900 -3.3600 -3.5400

Maximum values:

900.0 785.0 2560.0 11438.0 9622.1 3680.8 1.2079 1.2080 1.2068
 535.50 800.30 708.70 .2478 .0205 .9959
 .00 .00 .00 59.19 3.34 3.2100 3.4000 3.4100

STATISTICS OF DIFFERENCE, FILE 1 - FILE 2

Mean values:

.0 .0 .0 -.2 -6.8 -6.8 .0000 .0000 .0000
 .04 -.02 .05 .0000 .0000 .0002
 .0000 .0000 .0000
 .00 .00 .00 3.86 -.01 -.0021 -.0026 -.0005

MS values:

.0 .0 .0 19.2 39.8 31.4 .0014 .0010 .0038
 .63 2.29 1.24 .0016 .0001 .0057
 .0014 .0010 .0038
 .00 .00 .00 4.07 1.12 .1302 .1342 .1012

Minimum values:

.0 .0 .0 -123.9 -277.6 -176.5 -.0070 -.0056 -.0246
 -6.30 -17.70 -12.30 -.0010 -.0008 -.0046
 -.0070 -.0056 -.0246
 .00 .00 .00 -.02 -4.52 -.4700 -.4700 -.3900

Maximum values:

.0 .0 .0 125.9 211.8 178.3 .0441 .0054 .1670
 6.50 18.70 14.80 .0752 .0008 .2780
 .0441 .0054 .1671
 .00 .00 .00 7.67 3.38 .3600 .3800 .3000

Correlation coefficients:

1.0000 1.0000 1.0000 1.0000 1.0000 .9999 1.0000 1.0000 1.0000
 1.0000 1.0000 1.0000 .9921 .9999 .9938
 .9834 .9904 .9700
 .0000 .0000 .0000 .9989 .3730 .9918 .9912 .9950